

Strategic and Ethical Deployment of Generative AI in Business Operations: Case Studies in Pharmaceutical Marketing and Sustainable Retail

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Abstract

In this modern era, AI adoption is rising significantly across different sectors. However, this also comes with the difficulty of ethical implementation. Businesses aiming to integrate AI in their daily operations must be aligned with ethical, regulatory and business goals. Challenges in terms of compliance, trust, bias and operational readiness are faced at the moment by business in versatile sectors. The purpose of this study is to explore the ethical and strategic deployment of Generative AI across two different industries. We present two different use cases, GSK associated with the pharmaceutical industry and Too Good to Go with the sustainable retail. In the former one, we integrated Open AI's GPT models to automate a number of tasks in the department of marketing, sales and administrative tasks in order to make the business operations more efficient and productive and in the later one, we implemented Agentic AI to optimize the day-to-day tasks of the business such as dynamic pricing, food surplus classification and autonomous customer on-boarding and routing. The emphasis was on ethical and regulatory compliance (FDA, EMA), human-in-the-loop systems and internal governance to ensure ethical use of the aforementioned technologies.

The methodology involved a phased implementation plan which involved agile planning, risk analysis performance indicators and ROI projections. Additionally, we combine technical planning with much needed ethical safeguards which include fairness audits, data security and privacy, and workforce up-skilling. Through this paper it is demonstrated that ethically grounded AI strategies deliver tangible and exponential results. Lastly, we highlighted the potential of such AI technologies to enhance profitability and showcased responsible innovation as a competitive edge and not just an ethical responsibility.

1 Introduction and Context

We are proposing to integrate OpenAI's GPT into the marketing department of the company GSK. GSK (GlaxoSmithKline) is a UK based biopharmaceutical company. Their main products are pharmaceuticals, vaccines and consumer healthcare products such as Sensodyne, Panadol and Voltaren. Through this integration we hope to make the marketing channels and content more effective and workflows more efficient.

AI powered tools such as GPTs have gained traction in all industries and now are a vital part of them. In our case the pharmaceutical industry is looking to integrate AI in their marketing process for efficiency and ethical responsibility.

The following sections introduce the purposes and scope of exploring AI integration in Pharma marketing, its growing relevance and a strategic game plan.

2 Strategic Relevance of AI in Marketing Function

It is important to understand that pharma marketing demands precision, regulation compliance and most importantly patient safety. We have to strategize in such a way that we get our message out

without attracting any legal issues. Hence, the AI will help in a number of areas which are concentrated as follows,

Automation of Content generation
Personalized marketing targeting specific and diverse demographics
Cross-language/ Cross-Platform campaigns

This implementation of AI in marketing should be scalable and of course reliable with respect to the aforementioned problems.

3 Corporate Responsibility in Pharma Innovation

Corporate responsibility in such sensitive areas and fields is very important. Misinformation in health-care can mislead patients or professionals leading to unfortunate and serious health problems as well as legal problems. In addition to that, Pharma is governed by strict marketing laws such as FDA, EMA and such so AI generated content must be vetted and so there has to be a human in loop.

According to the FDA [1], they don't oversee every single ad before it is released, however certain companies ask for their advice before planning or integrating advertisements. Hence, historical data for such interactions can be useful while prompting the AI for our strategies. The evaluation criteria will be judged across the following metrics,

Accuracy AI should not fabricate clinical claims or sensitive information such as dosage instructions and such and outputs must be fact checked against approved medical data.

Transparency User disclaimers or symbols must be used to maintain honesty with healthcare providers and consumers.

Long-term trust and Brand reputation AI governance is required to build trust with customers and regulators hence good ethical practices insure AI is sustainable and beneficial. In addition to that, brand reputation is also important while transitioning or integrating AI because mistakes due to irresponsible AI can trigger reputational crises bad for short and long-term success.

Internal Oversight We have to form AI review boards and internal audits keeping the AI content in context. Regular assessments of AI outputs are necessary to catch and correct issues correctly.

4 OpenAI: Tools and Capabilities

OpenAI is a leading AI research and deployment company preemptively known for its GPT models and Codex and initially DALL-E. This is a major player when it comes to AI technologies and of course the central player when it comes to debates around AI governance and ethics.

Established as a Non-profit organization the fundamental mission of OpenAI was to ensure that Artificial General Intelligence benefits all humanity. As TealHQ states [2], this is a reflection of their long term goal to develop powerful yet safe technology and an emphasis on global cooperation in AI development.

5 OpenAI for GSK Marketing

The core reason to use efficient tools such as GPT Enterprise is because it offers a high language fluency and multilingual capacity. It can be highly personalized to stay compliant and of course can be scalable and flexible.

These factors ensure that we are not reinventing the wheel rather than integrating the AI technology into our already implemented workflows. This is important for access control and keeping humans in loop.

Following are few targeted use cases,

Product Content Creation GPT can generate brand aligned descriptions for prescription drugs, supplements or even treatments. These shall be useful for digital marketing and of course more traditional methods such as websites and brochures.

Ideation AI shall be used for brainstorming headlines, emails and advertisements. Ensuring maximum customer engagement and with OpenAI's Codex this can be automated with just a few lines of code.

Multilingual Marketing Translate the marketing assets while being consistent with tone and compliance as well as adjust to cultural references for regional accuracy.

Competitor Analysis Here we can use GPT to digest market reports, social media buzz and news to extract relevant trends and information that may be valuable for counter-marketing.

6 Project Value and Impact

Integration of GPT is not just a technical upgrade but more of a strategic move when business decisions are concerned. From streamlining content to increase in customer engagement this move will put the company both as an innovator and a leader in the market. The key projected business outcomes from this move are as follows

6.1 Accelerated Campaigns

The time and energy required to implement a marketing campaign from brainstorming to deployment is a lot and definitely a hefty process. This can be cut in half by the integration of AI powered tools. So, repetitive or time consuming tasks such as reviewing drafts or writing content can be automated.

This will result in more time set for more creative tasks and also results in quicker prototypes which means quicker market-to-go execution.

6.2 Boost in Innovation Culture

Innovation is one thing that a human mind excels. Creative thinking is important when it comes to marketing so this integration shall encourage cross-functional AI collaboration. Teams will be able to explore new innovative marketing channels and formats in order to gain maximum engagement.

6.3 Cost Optimization

This is an important factor to consider because through AI we will be less dependent on external copywriters and translators. Hence, this newly saved budget can be reallocated to creative strategies.

6.4 Enhanced Customer Experience

Customer engagement is of the utmost importance not just for the evaluation but as a feedback for future cases too. Engagement rate and customer satisfaction can be increased by techniques such as niche and highly tailored chatbots which provide personalized context-aware responses which can be used on websites or apps.

6.5 Competitive Edge

This move will give us an edge over the slower moving competitors. As we shall be able to do more vigorous A/B and/or Pilot testing with AI generated variants and fine-tune accordingly without the need for iteration after deployment.

7 Financial Analysis

The integration of OpenAI's tech into our marketing department as mentioned before will be cost-saving and shall provide new avenues for revenue generation. A strategic financial analysis has been done which will reveal key factors such as cost breakdown, revenue potential and ROI which will be useful for long-term sustainability.

7.1 Cost Breakdown

Although the upfront investment required for software tools is significant, the ongoing costs are minimal to the potential gains. The initial costs shall include,

Software Licensing which covers the subscription fee for GPT based services. Based on the current market rates, the cost for enterprise-level access for GPT services range from \$75,000 to \$150,000 per year, depending on the number of licenses required.

Integration and Development Costs include the integration of tools into existing workflows such as IT infrastructure, employee training and development which ranges from \$300,000 to \$450,000. This includes upgrades and/or complete rehaul of the above mentioned areas.

Internal Oversight Team shall include staff to oversee the generated output to ensure it adheres to ethical standards and legal guidelines. Based on industry best practices, the annual cost of such staff typically ranges from \$100,000 to \$300,000. For the current forecast, we shall approximate it to \$165,000 annually.

7.2 Revenue Potential

By integration of the proposed tools and technologies we are projecting to see 20% to 30% increase in engagement rates which have a solid potential to add \$8m to \$12m in annual revenue.

Additionally, through this we can accelerate our marketing campaigns leading to \$50m to \$75m increase in revenue thanks to the quicker product launches. Similarly, the revenue potential increases through cross-functional teams because of versatile skills and targeting personalization through multilingual content.

7.3 Return on Investment

If we talk about short-term gains then the proposed system is projected to save around \$600k to \$800k in the first quarter after deployment, with the cost recovery of around \$550k in the first year. However, in the long-run projections show around 20% to 25% improvement in the success rate of our campaigns, leading to an additional \$30m increase in revenue over our 3 year plan.

$$\text{ROI} = \frac{\text{Net Profit}}{\text{Total Investment}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

The formula above is used to project short-term and long-term gains from our integration, one thing to note is that the net profit includes the operational savings as well as additional revenue streams.

Last but not least, ethical AI integration will significantly lower the liabilities connected to autonomous marketing and prevent legal risks in order to maintain our organization's reputation and support long-term ROI.

8 Ethics and Risk Factors

As the pharma industry adopts AI tools, ethical and regulatory issues must be acknowledged and adequately addressed. The tools although are powerful and increase efficiency but have the challenges of their own discussed as follows.

8.1 Biases in AI

This is a major problem when it comes to development of models. The root cause of biases in machine prediction is the type of data which we use to train it. GPTs often reflect societal and/or training data biases. In our case it is more concerning as we may be under the risk of biased medical content such as age, race or gender of a client.

Vicente and Matute (2023) [3] showcased that, after 3 experiments related to exploration of biases in AI it was concluded that the biased recommendations by the AI influenced the participants' decisions. Hence, to counter this the content must be audited and human-in-loop should be implemented at all stages. This is important as we don't want to reinforce stereotypes when it comes to global marketing.

8.2 Hallucinations

Hallucinations are also an important aspect when it comes to AI generated content. Zeff (2025) [4] highlights, OpenAI's o3 and o4 mini are expected to be state of the art models which include reasoning that tend to hallucinate more after internal testing.

There is no solid answer as to why models do so; however in our case there is a high risk of inaccurate or hallucinated dosage and contraindications. This again can be countered by humans who shall validate every output especially in high-risk content where there are elevated liability concerns.

8.3 Data Protection

There are going to be a lot of data concerns as we are using patient data such as reviews, feedback and so on which also raise GDPR/ PHI concerns. This can be countered if we use synthetic data or anonymize the already collected data so that it becomes unidentifiable. Additionally, access control should be implemented with role-based access and continuous logging for sensitive AI tasks.

8.4 Workforce Implications

When we automate repetitive or even complex tasks, manual roles are reduced. This can lead to mass job displacement within an organization. McKinsey (2024) [6] estimated that approximately 75 million to 375 million may need to switch their jobs and learn new skills.

This means that we need to upskill our workforce and internal communication should reflect augmentation not replacement.

8.5 Compliance and Legal Assessments

Our strategy must align with GDPR, EU AI Act and of course pharma specific frameworks such as FDA, EMA and HIPAA. Documentation and logging is of vital importance in order to enhance transparency and traceability. Hence, legal and medical teams should be involved in all deployment

9 Roadmap to Responsible Adoption

The strategic recommendations although are a lot but are concentrated into the following 4 points,

9.1 Integration Approach

Our main focus before full scale deployment is pilot testing in controlled environments. Starting with low-risk internal briefings and drafts then moving on to customer-facing tools with strong oversight. This will not only help with the adoption but also good for the models themselves when appropriate training is concerned.

9.2 Internal Governance

We aim to establish an internal AI ethics committee consisting of members from different departments such as Legal, Marketing, Compliance and such. Workflows of content review shall be created such as pre-approval, feedback iterations and such. Additionally regular audits shall be done to assess performance and both technical and internal.

9.3 Cross-functional Collaboration

For unbiased review we aim to collaborate with external ethics consultants and of course academic advisors. Other departments will collaborate accordingly such as HR for workforce upskilling, IT and Cybersecurity for data handling and protection and of course Legal and Compliance to assess regulatory alignments.

9.4 Safeguards for Ethical Use

As mentioned before we shall maintain human-in-the-loop for all our published content. Literacy training will be conducted to up-skill everyone involved. Lastly, we aim to monitor post-deployment impact via feedback and internal analyses.

10 Extending Ethical AI to the Food Sustainability Sector

Building on the insights gained from the process of integration of AI, responsibly specially in domain where ethical consideration is of the utmost importance. Human oversight and regulatory compliance are the backbone of a successful AI adoption regardless of the industry.

The following case explores the application of Agentic AI within a Denmark based company called Too Good to Go. We will explore and study how autonomous agents can tackle operational challenges such as dynamic pricing, surplus prediction and hyper-personalized customer engagement to optimize efficiency and environmental impact.

11 Business Problem Definition and Investment Case

The company we are working with to propose solutions is Condamine (2020) [7] Too Good To Go. Founded in Denmark in 2016, the company belongs to the social impact industry and focuses on food reduction operations. The aim is to connect businesses that have surplus food to customers which may benefit from the food instead of going to waste.

The revenue model is basically business set a price for their surprise bags for the customers and Too Good To Go acts as a mediator and takes 25% to 35% from each transaction as a commission fee.

12 Strategic Challenge Overview

There are a number of challenges faced by the company at this point in time. Firstly they use a static pricing method and are overdependent on it. The limited dynamic prices lead to substandard clearance rates. Additionally, the restaurant they partner with have a manual entry with their surplus which means that often they input surplus inventory manually which can be often incorrect but more importantly can miss real-time demand patterns.

Next comes the problem of zones, the balance between densely and sparsely populated zones is important to manage because it creates a difference in user engagement and food rescue efficiency. Similarly, personalizations used at this moment don't integrate behavioral and contextual insights which can be capitalized.

Lastly, operations of the company are semi-automated hence they struggle with scalability. In addition to that, lack of automations results in lack of coordination in surplus forecasting and user availability. From this another problem emerges which is due to the aforementioned rigid surplus-to-customer flow the food often expires before any purchases which again is a wastage which we can overcome through automations at the right places.

13 Business Process Analysis

The following section highlights the business processes of the organization along with their shortcomings.

13.1 Data Silos and Customer Interaction

Real-time data flow is important in order to come up with an autonomous robust system. The restaurants, users and logistics don't share a unified data flow which then results in problems arising from lack of communication.

On the other hand, the customer feedback is not integrated into the surplus organization and offer timing. This is important because feedback of the end-user basically defines how you will align the product according to the market demands.

13.2 Manual Ways and Limited Collaboration

POS integration is important because it enables us to accurately calculate the surplus declaration. Manual ways of the restaurant are delayed due to underlying reasons and are often less accurate. Similarly, there is no autonomous arrangement between merchants, users and of course the delivery windows. Crystal clear communication and collaboration is of the utmost importance in order to be efficient and create a win-win situation just like the company envisions Too Good To Go [8].

13.3 Suboptimal Routing

The coordination of an agent for delivery is not optimized in order to reduce customer travel and food spoilage. The routes should be calculated in order to reduce travel time which will also be more efficient and save relevant resources.

13.4 Cost Structure and Performance Impact

When cost structure is concerned then at the top of the list is lack of autonomous systems. Human resources are drained in processes such as inventory reporting as mentioned before, similarly training and onboarding of the employee also result in loss of resources which can be used elsewhere. According to Growjo (2020), Too Good To Go has approximately 1580 employees and is growing year by year. Although, partner support cost is not publicly available for the company, however according to the Annual report of a similar company the partner support cost was approximately €12m to €18m per year and through approximations we can conclude that a similar number is seen by Too Good To Go by Growjo (n.d.) [9]. This number along with the approximate number of employees can be benefited and cut with automating certain processes.

If we talk about performance impact then one point to note is that continuous churn diminishes the returns especially due to the acquired users who stop engaging after 2 to 3 purchases. This also creates an opportunity for more revenue because at this moment there is no non-personalized outreach to retain the customers and re-engagement rates are weak.

Furthermore, refunds, quality inconsistencies and negative reviews also create a burden on operational costs and untapped potential from demand patterns and surplus trends also don't help in increasing the efficiency.

14 Goals for Agentic AI Intervention

As mentioned above a number of processes can be automated through agents and implementation roadmap for key pain points are as follows.

14.1 Autonomous Surplus Prediction Agents

This agent will predict the inventory surplus with higher accuracy according to each merchant and will be achieved by integrating the POS with historical data and weather forecast. The expected surplus for a merchant can be estimated by a weighted sum of contributing factors:

$$S_t = \alpha H_t + \beta W_t + \gamma D_t \quad (2)$$

Where S_t is the surplus at time t , H_t represents historical data, W_t is the weather impact factor, and D_t reflects demand patterns. The weights α, β, γ are calibrated based on prior performance.

14.2 Dynamic Setting of Price and Agents

Here we shall set up an agent which automatically adjusts the surprise bag price and quantity according to its time of expiry, demand spikes and the feasibility of delivery. This price adjustment can be guided by a time-decay model:

$$P_t = P_0 \cdot e^{-\lambda t} \quad (3)$$

Where P_t is the adjusted price at time t , P_0 is the original listing price, and λ is a decay constant tuned to account for perishability and real-time demand dynamics.

14.3 Hyper-personalized Engagement and Demand Balancing Agents

Personalized offer agents will scale user satisfaction and conversion by recommending hyper-local and contextually aware food rescue opportunities. These will utilize the patterns from time-based ordering, diet constraint and behavioral clustering in order to segment the user. User clusters are formed by minimizing intra-group variance:

$$J = \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{x \in C_i} \|x - \mu_i\|^2 \quad (4)$$

Where J is the clustering loss, C_i denotes the i -th cluster, and μ_i is the centroid of that cluster.

Additionally, they will act as middle-man merchants, users and the company itself to create a balance between stock clearance, dynamic price and sustainable development goals. The system ensures an ideal alignment between supply and demand in order to create a marketplace that learns and adapts per user segment according to each city.

14.4 Self-Learning Operational Scaling Agents

To ensure sustainable international scaling and localized campaigns, we are proposing a set of city-level optimization agents which will predict the restaurants recruitment needs, ideal pickup locations and marketing intensity with the help of geographic trends and demand signals.

All agents operate according to a Scalable ROI Architecture that ensures the aforementioned automations reduce operational costs, the cost for expansion and operates across cities with minimal bur critical overhead.

15 Market Context and AI Solution Exploration

The section explores the market the business is in and potential solutions for the aforementioned challenges.

15.1 Industry Benchmarks and Competitive AI

The emphasis on reduction of food waste is growing exponentially and has triggered an industry wide-innovation in relevant technology. To counteract this certain supermarkets and merchants are using AI to optimize their inventory and reduce food wastage. For instance, some platforms are making use of computer vision integrated with geolocation to classify waste sources dynamically which is huge for this industry.

On the other hand, the younger population now explicitly expects the brands to reduce their food wastage and carbon footprints. So, for a smoother transition policies such as EU's Farm to Fork strategy are fostering AI based automatic waste auditing. Next, AI powered analytics are integrated with it to showcase live tracking of sustainability KPIs for transparency. Piterman et al. (2025) [11] analyze while studying OLIOs algorithm suggested further improvements in the machine learning model which could foster community engagement and provide strategic methods for the future.

15.2 Competitor Analysis

Direct competitors such as OLIO, Karma, Phenix and HelloFresh use advanced algorithms such as Behavioral Machine Learning Matching to cluster users in order to prioritize food redistribution, use of AI-time notifications to save near-expiry food to go to waste, use of dynamic demand forecasting and logistics optimization, respectively.

It is safe to say that Too Good To Gos competitors are shifting towards adoption of relevant AI technologies hence to stay ahead of the market we need to integrate such technology in daily operations too.

16 Agentic AI Application

There are a number of applications for Agentic AI tech in this field autonomous-agents can act on behalf of different actors in the cycle which will allow real-time negotiations. In addition to that, self-initiating agents can predict and prevent food surplus without any external prompts. Moreover, we can make use of bidding bots to dynamically bid for excess food depending on different factors.

Similarly, we can use federated learning to enhance anonymous sharing of inter-city information, Norm-adaptive agents to reflect values and norms to better fit the requirements and preferences of the customers.

17 Proposed Agentic AI System for Too Good To Go

First and foremost we are proposing a distributed multi-agent system which comprises autonomous agents performing versatile roles such as merchants, consumers and classifiers. Through this we will implement an agent for surplus identification through an ensemble of image analysis and text classification to classify food into two classes i.e urgency and spoilage risk.

Our Recommendation Agent will make use of deep reinforcement learning in order to personalize food bundles based on the preference of the user and their behavioral data. Last but not least our autonomous onboarding agent will provide our partners with onboarding, training and integration support from a guided interaction.

Through the integration of these agents critical areas will be autonomous for better efficiency and productivity. All of these integrations will be done while keeping the human in loop in order to oversee all aspects.

18 Feasibility and Integration

We will make use of the current infrastructure with minimal additions. First we will leverage current APIs and dashboards for a smoother transition to integrate our agents. The focus is on event driven architecture and the use of Kafka, Akın (2023) [12], suggests that Kafka provides high throughput reliability and fault tolerance which will be perfect for our use-case.

Next we will make use of Docker and Kubernetes to deploy scalable and region-specific containerized AI agents. Docker will help us containerize these agents and Kubernetes will enable us to deploy such containers in an automated fashion, Enterprise Project (2020) [13] details.

To ensure privacy we will make use of edge-computing in order to localize all the processing. For seamless negotiations between agents we will make use of protocols such as gRPC which are basically remote procedure calls to build scalable and robust APIs for a transparent and smoother communication Wallarm (n.d.) [14] explains.

Lastly, to train our agents we will create a simulation on Unity to replicate real food flow in order to better train the agents by mimicking real world implications. In order to scale, we will use Azure with auto-scaling and optimize our GPUs to make things ready for a global roll-out in the near future.

19 Agentic AI Strategy Design

The following section explores how we develop and deploy the aforementioned technologies into the daily operations.

19.1 Aim Objectified

To attain this, the project will follow some secondary goals. This includes basically improving the regulation of partner onboarding, which is currently a resource intensive manual process.

Moreover, the system will aim to outstandingly increase the excess permission rate through dynamic pricing and smart matching, while increasing user personalization to promote greater engagement and loyalty.

Success will be explained by a clear set of measurable metrics: a minimum 20% improvement in the excess permission rate within the experiment market, a 15% cut in user churn due to enhanced personalization, and a bisecting of the time required for new partners to become fully functional on the platform. The experiment will be launched in Barcelona, a large, multiple urban market that provides an ideal proving ground for agent dynamics across a multiplex landscape of partners and consumers.

The project timeline is projected for a step by step launch over 3 quarters. Additionally, this move requires close collaboration with both internal and external stakeholders. The system's modular building is a key design principle, guaranteeing it is built for future expandability over Europe and can be adapted to different local food laws and market conditions.

20 Project Implementation Timeline

As mentioned before the implementation is divided into 3 quarters which includes a multi-phase roadmap to reduce risk, and includes a feedback loop approach to ensure a smooth transition.

20.1 Quarter 1 July- September

In this quarter we will plan and design the architecture. This includes collecting requirements from the user and partners. The main aim is to deploy a multiagent system of versatile agents as discussed previously complete with communication channels, data flow and collaboration with Too Good To Be trues legacies systems.

After appropriate planning we will work on our prototype. This will include creation and training of the core agents. These prototypes will be developed over a controlled environment and will be sandboxed to test accordingly.

20.2 Quarter 2 October- December

Better part of this quarter will be solely for testing and running simulations. We will test system flexibility and inter-agent working. We will simulate real life scenarios and through this feedback loop we will keep iterating our agents to interact and optimize the outcome in order to be better fit for testing.

After two months of vigorous testing we will prepare for our alpha phase in the last month and roll it out. This will include a small set of trusted partners. During alpha testing we will closely monitor KPIs and compare the results with the results of our simulations.

20.3 Quarter 3 January-March

In this quarter we will launch our beta phase expanding to more districts and sectors. With increased independence and autonomous coordination we will remain in beta test for a month. After appropriate alterations if needed we will prepare for a proper full scale launch after preparation.

After full scale deployment we will move towards monitoring. Here, we will deploy visual dashboards for transparency and overview. The final month will consist of audits regarding performance, security and ethics to ensure fairness and privacy.

21 Risk Analysis and Mitigation Strategies

Through risk assessment we have identified a number of key risks for our agents and to ensure we comply with crisis magnet techniques we have also developed mitigation strategies for such risks.

21.1 Key Risks

ARIS (2025) [15] states that a business should not leave the future to chance but should always analyze risks and costs in order to mitigate them if things go south. As we know the performance of the model depends on the quality of the data. Hence, factors such as bias are of critical importance. Prior to this we made sure that we use data which has no biases however in a scenario in which we face such circumstances then to counteract that we will conduct careful audits using fairness metrics to

detect and correct any biases in food allotment. To ensure data privacy we implemented state-of-the-art privacy preserving techniques such as differential privacy and use of federated learning and ensure compliance with all existing data protection frameworks. The risk of over reliance is always there when such technologies are concerned hence we include human-in-loop to ensure oversight at every stage. Lastly, we will remain transparent and open with channels for communication in order to strengthen the brand's reputation.

22 Resource and Cross-functional Teams

Our development consists of a group comprising 5 people,

- AI engineers for agentic AI architecture
- Reinforcement Learning Engineer
- XAI Engineer
- Operations Lead

23 Budget Allocation

Our budget allocation is as follows,

- €750,000 for computational resources and cloud costs and HR needed.
- €150,000 as our partner incentive budget and navigating food handling and ethical checks
- €75,000 for UI and UX development and deployment
- Contingency fund (10% of the total fund)

24 Implementation Plan and ROI Framework

This section explores our implementation plan and our ROI framework.

24.1 Breakdown and Justification

The total estimated expenditure for our project divided into 3 quarters is almost €975,000. The budget is planned to acquire necessary human resources, computational resources and support systems for a planned and smooth execution.

According to the amount listed above and the previously mentioned budget allocation this cost will cover the salaries of our personnel, our infrastructure both physical and cloud dedicated simulation and testing equipment and lastly a 10

24.2 Operational Savings Projection

The integration of Agentic AI and Gen AI in business operations now are important as they allow the top management to rethink how humans work and make the change management even more critical Mueller et al. (2025) [16] recommends. The change management is both in terms of creativity and innovation through which business see increase in revenue and decrease in operational costs. The integration of our Agentic AI ecosystem is projected to generate solid operational savings. These savings are a keystone of the project's ROI.

The major part of our savings are from reduction in manual workload. Our autonomous onboarding agent handles the entire process from initial inquiry to full activation which reduces a huge number of human resources needed during this process. Similarly, the surplus classification agent automates the marking and classification of items which again was a manual process before.

The key thing to note is that this isn't a case of job displacement as these human resources can be used in creative works where human intelligence is critical. However, jointly these automations are projected automations will reduce the required work hours in the relevant sectors by approximately 35

If we talk specifically about our agents then our dynamic pricing agent will increase the efficiency of the food sold by 20%. Our autonomous routing agent will allocate surprise bags and save your partners up to 12% of the total cost associated with it. Additionally, personalized recommendations will reduce the acquisition cost by 15% and partners are expected to see a reduction of 18% in waste related fees. These projections overall will benefit internal and external stakeholders with not only automated work but with operational savings as well.

24.3 Revenue Growth Opportunities Through Integration

On one side our system will reduce operational costs and on the other hand it will create new channels for revenue. Here are a few options we aim to explore regarding the new opportunities.

- Through API Licensing we can leverage our experienced and trained Agentic AI backend as an enterprise solution to third party companies.
- Through our Branded Ethical AI label we can further increase the brand's trust and attract viable conscious users.
- We can make use of trend insights from legalized and undisclosed food flow data for B2B data insights.
- From Sponsored Surplus campaigns our agents can promote a specific product for a specifically targeted market.

25 Key Performance Indicators

To measure our success and impact we have prepared a few KPIs across business outcomes, technical performance and operational order and are as follows,

- Clearance Rate KPI: Increase our surprise bag clearance from 64
- Agent's Accuracy KPI: Preserve a 92
- User Retention KPI: From the pilot zone attain a 20
- Onboarding KPI: Reduce the average onboarding time from 2 days to 12 hours.
- Partners NPS KPI: Achieve an increase of 15 points in partner's Net Promoter Score post Agentic Integration.
- Environmental Impact KPI: Achieve the projected reduction of 150 tons of CO2 emissions in the first 2 quarters.
- Through these KPIs we will be able to test the impact of our integrations on the business both through savings of operational costs and new channels for revenue. The integrations will surely allow Too Good To Go to compete with the competitors in order to lead the market.

26 Conclusion

The study has exhibited the strategic and ethical deployment of AI technologies in two distinct industries: pharmaceuticals and sustainable retail. The former through integration of GPT models in business operations, and the latter through the integration of Agentic AI automation. We also highlighted the importance of regulatory compliance and ethical considerations in such sensitive domains. The aim is not just to develop and deploy artificial intelligence for a technical edge over the market, but to focus on ethical deployment to be sustainable and foster growth.

The defined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) provide quantifiable benchmarks to assess the performance of our deployed systems. Achieving these will solidify the dual value proposition of AI as a tool for financial goals as well as social responsibility. The study emphasized responsible innovation as a holistic approach and not just a technological upgrade, perfectly balancing innovation, accountability, and business value. The frameworks and methodologies presented here serve as actionable blueprints for organization aiming to adopt AI responsibly and advocate for AI development strategies for not only competitiveness but for sustainability in this modern era.

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